

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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- Medical University of Warsaw (**MUW**)
- Stichting het Nederlands kankerinstituut-Antoni Van Leeuwenhoek ziekenhuis (**NKI-AVL**)
- Sciensano (**SCI**)

List of abbreviations

AJCC, American joint committee on cancer
AML, acute myeloid leukemia
CHIP, clonal hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential
CLL, chronic lymphocytic leukemia
CNV, copy number variation
CRC, colorectal cancer
CRO, contract research organization
dPCR, digital polymerase chain reaction
FFPE, formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded
GL, germline
HM, hematological malignancies
LB, liquid biopsy
LumA, luminal A type breast cancer
MBL, monoclonal B lymphocytosis

MRD, minimal residual disease
MSI, microsatellite instability
MTA/DTA, material and data transfer agreements
NED, no evidence of disease
NGS, next-generation sequencing
NSCLC, non-small cell lung cancer
PBMNC, peripheral blood mononuclear cell
SNV, single nucleotide variant
SOM, somatic
TMB, tumor mutational burden
VAF, variant allele frequency
VUS, variant of unknown significance

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Summary

D25 is one of three closely related deliverables planned for WP7 being released in rapid succession. WP7 established four clinical pilots focused on non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), colorectal cancer (CRC), luminal A type breast cancer (LumA), and hematological malignancies (HM). This approach aims to maximize the capture not only of individual cancer risk, but also familial predisposition or precursor states of overt hematological malignancies. This document addresses steps undertaken to harmonize multi-center recruitment and delocalized testing, material and data exchange, to implement a strategy for role-dependent inclusion of the participating centers, as well as data collection and sharing. We analyze study flowchart flowchart to objectively measure success and troubleshoot individual bottlenecks. We describe cBioportal implementation, by providing representative snapshots showing that we can graphically outline per-patient views and longitudinal (e.g. liquid biopsy) representations of minimal residual disease throughout follow-up. Due to delays in MTA/DTA signature, data collection and data sharing steps are not yet complete. However, implementation of the Can.HEAL model reveals useful bypass measures and data sharing approaches that will strengthen EU collaboration in future large multicenter trials.

Not all activities were completed as intended (estimated progress 80%) due to a number of bottlenecks. However, the results so far obtained align with the objectives set out in the workplan. Most importantly, the Can.HEAL partners have now identified original strategies to design, coordinate and expedite the process of generating a highly integrated sequence of Material Transfer, Data Transfer, Data Processing and Service Level Agreements (MTA/DTA/DPA/SLA). To our knowledge, such an extensive troubleshooting had not been attempted earlier in any EU-wide clinical pilots. D25 was submitted with a delay of 3 weeks.

Objective of the deliverable

- Foreword

D25 is the last one in a series of three closely related WP7 deliverables, being released in rapid succession. It is being released after D24 and simultaneously with D23.

D24: T7.2 - Task leader ICO.

Integration of NGS and clinical data. NGS data available in the framework of clinical information.

Due Jan 31st (**submitted**)

D23: T7.1 - Task leader ACC.

NGS testing data. 40 evaluable patients tested, raw and curated NGS data. Link with ELBS (WP11) to address technical NGS issues.

Due Feb 28th

D25: T7.3 - Task leader NKI-AVL.

Data transfer to WP3 for HTA evaluation.

Due Feb 28th (**This deliverable**)

In D24, recently submitted, the Can.HEAL Consortium provided an overview of the context, clinical pilot study plan, rationale, primary aim, logistics, testing and task distribution. The reader is referred to D24 for these details, that will be briefly recalled herein to introduce the specific aims of D25.

- WP7 objectives in the context of CAN.HEAL

Can.HEAL is a collaborative project funded by the EU4Health program. The size of the Consortium and the distribution of the Partners across EU (Fig. 1) show wide representation of local healthcare diversity. Therefore, Can.HEAL set as its ambitious primary aim to explore models of future

Participating countries:

1. Belgium
2. Czech Republik
3. Denmark
4. Estonia
5. France
6. Germany
7. Greece
8. Italy
9. Latvia
10. Luxembourg
11. Malta
12. Netherlands
13. Poland
14. Portugal
15. Serbia (Associated Partner)
16. Slovenia
17. Spain

39 beneficiaries
7 affiliated entities
1 associated partner

Fig. 1. Can.HEAL partners

collaborative trials in EU. A dedicated clinical work package (WP7) was established to address these challenges. WP7 focuses on specific use cases involving colorectal cancer (CRC), non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), luminal A type breast cancer (LumA), and hematological malignancies (HM) associated with clonal

hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential (CHIP) and/or monoclonal B lymphocytosis (MBL). The common denominator of these pilots, that focus on early cancer and known cancer-predisposing clinical conditions, is to capture cancer risk. Risk is defined as both the individual risk for the patient

to undergo relapse/progression, and for family members to inherit cancer-predisposition. Most pilots focus on young patients with early-stage disease at high risk of relapse.

Biological samples, genomic data, clinical-pathological information, and medical imaging data have been prospectively collected and are undergoing retrospective analysis. These WP7 clinical pilots are central to the CAN.HEAL EU-wide data collection strategy. The diagram in Fig. 2 summarizes the shared design of the 4 pilots.

Fig. 2. Can.HEAL clinical pilots. Four pilots were designed. Three of them explore tissue and blood (liquid biopsy) readouts in the early setting (curative intent). Three solid tumors were investigated: Colorectal Cancer (CRC); Breast Cancer (BrCa), and Lung cancer (NSCLC). The fourth pilot is about the capture of gene variants associated with Clonal Hematopoiesis of indetermined Potential (CHIP) and Monoclonal B cell expansions in the hematological setting.

All data, including genetic/genomic information, clinical-pathological data, and medical imaging data, are being shared on a common ICT platform for integrated analysis. This work aims at demonstrating the feasibility and potential gain of a federated, EU-wide approach to precision oncology trials, and its integration into common practice in the near future.

- The WP7 pilots

As shown in Fig. 3, all pilots have collected clinical and/or clinical pathological data, combined with molecular data, using common strategies and tools. The sources of molecular data were germ line DNA (gDNA), somatic DNA from tumor tissue (tDNA), and circulating tumor DNA from blood plasma (ctDNA). Testing of these three analytes was carried out with the 5 genomic tools listed in the inset of Fig. 3. Briefly, GerSom is a targeted NGS panel matching sequencing information from gDNA and tDNA to capture genomic alterations associated with familial predisposition in the former, and tumor specific alterations in the latter. Tumor-specific alterations are then used to set up bespoke digital PCR (dPCR) assays for tumor-informed search of Minimal Residual Disease in (MRD) in blood. Blood is also tested by tumor-agnostic NGS panels looking for additional genomic alterations, as well as DNA methylation and fragmentomic signatures. A different testing platform collects molecular data for the hematological pilot.

Fig. 3. Can.HEAL samples and genomic tools. The 4 pilots apply 5 tools to detect cancer alterations in the germ line and somatic lines in association with clinical pathological data. Genomic and epigenomic readouts (yellow box) are applied to tumor DNA (tDNA), circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), germ line DNA (gIDNA). Tools are a mixture of tumor agnostic and tumor-informed approaches. Minimal Residual Disease is actively looked for. Geneticists, Hematologists, Oncologists, and Biotechnologists form a team to interpret genomic endpoints, including incidental results such as germ line alterations, Clonal Hematopiesis, and other similar conditions. Hematology counseling is incorporated in the Can.HEAL concept. Additionally, hematologists run a separate use case. A special emphasis is placed on non-invasive approaches, particularly liquid biopsy (on ctDNA).

Work performed

- Data and material flowchart

The consortium elected to harmonize the collection/processing/distribution/sharing protocol (Fig. 4). Clinical data were collected at the recruiting sites in a form ready for annotation in a central repository. Clinical specimens/materials were also prospectively collected at 4 clinical sites, aliquoted and stored at local biobanks in a fully certified environment, and then shipped to the laboratories in charge of NGS/dPCR, e.g. the Partners in charge of generating molecular data. Clinical and molecular data follow two separate routes to reach the central repository, for recording/annotation and then interrogation and analysis, as outlined in Fig. 4.

Patient recruitment, testing and analysis are three separate activities in the Can.HEAL pilots. Not all the 15 participating centers from 12 Can.HEAL Partners perform in all of these roles. Only analysis is carried out by all their participants, and for this reason it is centralized in the online platform. It is also of note that as the materials and data move further in the workflow, data undergo a progressive refinement (Fig.5).

Fig. 5. Can.HEAL partners and their roles. There are three possible roles: recruiting, testing, and analyzing. These are carried out by 4, 7, and 15 partners. NKI-AVL supervises the final cBioportal data platform and also participates in analyzing the data. Each partner may play more than one role. Can.HEAL foresees steps and roles and a gradual change in the dataset, from primary to secondary data

The data collected in the dedicated Can.HEAL eCRF are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Graphical representation of the Can.HEAL eCRF and data to be shared. As intended, Can.HEAL combines pre-existing or newly generated information obtained from the germ line, somatic and blood (ctDNA) analytes. The information is classified in sections. Some epigenomic metrics are underlined.

Can.HEAL aims to share conventional genomic data and non-conventional epigenomic data. The latter readouts pose a distinctive annotation challenge.

The Can.HEAL workflow requires a data management plan aware of Partner role and data flowchart. To this end, three steps were undertaken, each of which is considered below: (a) fulfilment of a GDPR-compliant data processing protocol; (b) signature of material and data transfer agreements among 15 centers; (c) a data sharing plan to simplify data interrogation and exchange.

As to (a), the Partners agreed to have four levels of data access, as outlined in Fig. 7. Therefore, data is progressively de-identified, and yet at the recruitment site the data is still usable for therapeutic application to the individual patient. However, it was readily evident that not all the Partners apply the same GDPR rules for processing associated personal data. Therefore, despite the 4 steps envisaged, we had to empower a complex strategy for steps (b) and (c).

Fig. 7. GDPR compliance. Moving data and information from the recruiting sites to the end-users in the cBioportal platform results in the progressive data formatting process implying pseudo-anonymization, anonymization (at the testing labs). Scrambling the information in the shared platform results in GDPR-compliant federated data analysis.

As to (b), when modelling pilot trials, special efforts were devoted to keep the number of Material Transfer Agreements and Data Transfer Agreements (MTA/DTA) as low as possible. In the first place, a common MTA/DTA draft was generated and shared among the 15 involved institution, requesting the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) to determine whether this could be agreeable or major changes were needed.

After several consultation rounds it became evident that given the different partner roles, material/data exchanged, types of pilots, metrics involved, and the DPOs' decision to limit responsibilities, the preferred format was to have bilateral, dedicated, extensively modified MTA/DTA documents signed between any two partners (Fig. 8a). From rudimentary combinatorial calculation it was readily evident that this would imply a number of bilateral agreements largely exceeding the number of patients being recruited (Fig 8b). This irreducible limitation resulted in major WP delays (see below).

Fig. 8. Can.HEAL partners: a checkerboard to enumerate material and data transfer agreements. Combinatorial calculation shows that fulfillment of the basic required steps allowing exchange of information in a simple network of 15 partners with 3 different roles and 12 unique profiles results in more MTA/DTA documents (n= 66) than patients enrolled (n=65).

As to (c), it was evident, based on MTA/DTA experience, that applying a similar bilateral format to the exchange/interrogation of the data uploaded on cBioportal would result in similar delays, jeopardizing the entire WP7 pilot architecture. To avoid this, NKI strongly advised not to resort to hypothesis 1 (Fig. 9), that essentially mirrors the bilateral format of MTA/DTA and envisages each individual WP7 Partner/institute stipulating separate agreements for cBioportal access with Health RI. On the contrary, a simplified scheme was adopted, named hypothesis 2 (Fig. 9) whereby:

Fig. 9. Can.HEAL data management plan: simplifying clinical trial set-up. Rather than adopting a series of bilateral agreements defining unique biunivocal relationships among any two Can.HEAL Partners (as applied for MTA/DTA; Hypothesis 1), NKI-AVL applied a different model for DPA/SLA (hypothesis 2). In this simplified view, recruiting centers are moved to the middle. As data owners, they are central in the data sharing protocol, and release data through DPAs/SLAs to Health RI. In turn Health RI negotiates pre-planned access by interested partners. Interrogation may then be expanded but data owners retain control on the whole process.

- i. Recruiting centers enforce previous MTA/DTA to share data generated at the recruiting and testing sites
- ii. Recruiting centers retain the property of the above data
- iii. Recruiting sites negotiate with Health RI Data Processing Agreements and Service Level Agreements (DPA and SLA), and upload the data on the cBioportal/HelthRI platform
- iv. All WP7 partners request access to cBioportal under the responsibility/authorization of the clinical PIs of the pilots

Results

The available data have been structured to be recorded in a c-Bioportal–based central platform, as described (1). Unfortunately, due to delays in MTA/DTA signatures only a limited amount of data could be made available for upload. In the following chapters we will focus on bottlenecks, and will describe the cBioportal architecture.

- Bottlenecks in MTA/DTA

As described in D24, clinical pilots were successful in recruiting as well as obtaining clinical data and materials. There was remarkable flexibility. Through amendments and Ethical board approval of major amendments, we were able to accommodate even extensive changes in clinical practice during study requiring modifications in enrolment criteria. In sharp contrast, resorting to rigid, systematic bilateral formats of MTA/DTA agreements substantially halted most necessary procedures upstream data sharing. This was due to the combination of several factors, including:

- The negotiation format, requiring several versions and revisions of each bilateral document.
- A generalized, overly long turnaround time, for each revision until final approval
- A dyscoordination in the clearance of each step. Dyscoordination was particularly deleterious because of the combinatorial effect of four pilots (each focusing on a different tumor histotype), 6 testing platforms, 3 different partner roles and combination thereof. As a result, a single center was dealing at the same time with completely different documents proceeding at different speeds.
- Trivial bottlenecks, such as long inactivity at certain sites, and misunderstandings in the tracking status during complex document timelines.

In summary, the complexity of the whole procedure was more difficult to govern than the technical content of the specific documents. The following are representative benchmarks measuring the above bottlenecks altogether:

- Time to generate and circulate first draft: \approx 2 weeks (but shared documents prepared and discussed extensively since May 2023)
- Time to first feedback: 1 day - 5 months
- Average number of iterations: 9 (range 3-15)
- Time to agreement finalization: 5 – 9 months
- Time from MTA signature to material shipment: 3 days – 4+ months (ongoing delays)

- Time from shipment to testing: 1 month- unknown

Fig. 10. Practical steps and timeline for MTA/DTA signature. Landmark events during Can.HEAL

A summary of the entire timeline of MTA/DTA procedures spanning one and a half year (and not yet completed) is shown in Fig. 10.

«Virtuous»* example

* No delays but for summer holidays

Fig. 11. A selected example of MTA/DTA process. Seven landmark events that led to paperwork completion in slightly less than a year

Even in the best scenario, we were unable to keep the whole procedure below 11 months (Fig. 11).

Although these results are disappointing, many lessons were learnt (see below).

- The cBioportal as a data integration platform

The cBioPortal for Cancer Genomics is a data-integration platform designed for integrating multidimensional cancer (gen)omics datasets. The platform allows users, including non-bioinformaticians, to view, query and analyse the available data in a user friendly and intuitive manner that empowers them to understand complex, multidisciplinary data themselves.

The original cBioPortal (cbioportal.org) has 483 public studies available already, and well-described documentation is available on how to install a version of the tool yourself (see <https://docs.cbioportal.org/deployment/docker/>) and how to supply different types of data in the right format (see <https://docs.cbioportal.org/file-formats/>). Various research groups/institutes all over the world have installed a own dedicated cBioPortal instance (86 instances are reported on <https://installationmap.netlify.app/>, and there may be even more users who have installed a version for their own use).

On 29 March 2023, NKI and Health-RI organised a cBioPortal workshop for Can.Heal users and data loaders. During this workshop, an overview of the functionalities of cBioPortal was provided through

hands-on experience, using the Dutch national cBioPortal instance hosted by Health-RI (<https://www.health-ri.nl/services/cbioportal>), which was offered as a reference instance for this project. Workshop participants learnt how cBioPortal could be used for their study data and the steps involved with getting data onto this platform. These steps varied from e.g. modelling the different data types to cBioPortal-specific file formats, to e.g. reaching out to the ServiceDesk of Health-RI to initiate the required contracting to make use of the reference instance of cBioPortal. This Dutch national cBioPortal instance has authorised access procedures in place, which means that study data imported to this platform are not publicly available to everyone, but can be made available to collaborators and others after following a data access procedure. In short: it is the decision of the Principal Investigator of a study, who acts in an ELSI and GDPR compliant manner, to grant or deny study data access requests; so-called Health-RI operators, in this instance, then facilitate the decision of the Principal Investigator by performing the respective corresponding action (grant or deny access).

For the Belgian Precision initiative and BALLETT study part of WP9, researchers have performed a pilot to onboard their study data onto the Dutch national cBioPortal. Following the route as was explained during the workshop, and finalising the required contracting, BALLETT researchers were able to model the different types of data to cBioPortal-accepted file formats during a pilot phase, and currently have a subset of pseudonymised BALLETT patient data available in this cBioPortal instance.

Since the other studies in Can.Heal are in the preparation of collecting different data types and preparing for sharing the data (i.e. consortium agreements, data transfer/sharing agreements) no data of these studies were imported to cBioPortal. However, in this report, NKI can provide some recommendations and next steps for when the studies are ready for integrating the different data types that will have been obtained. Depending on the wishes and needs of the researchers in the time period beyond Can.Heal, either onboarding of their datasets can be performed by making use of the Dutch national cBioPortal instance and reaching out to the Health-RI ServiceDesk, or researchers can follow the steps as described on the public cBioPortal website to install a local version of cBioPortal themselves. In the future, it even may be that additional cBioPortal instances will become available across different European countries, e.g. because of projects like the Genomics Data Infrastructure or other projects that are currently working on a blueprint for IT infrastructure components that will be part of the EHDS landscape.

A key advantage of using cBioPortal is the subsequent data standardisation that is taking place. For import to cBioPortal, a user needs to model/transform the available data into a specific cBioPortal file-format, which then facilitates for data integration over different data types. The studies in Can.Heal entail both clinical and (gen)omis data – including longitudinal ctDNA data.

The (gen)omics data file formats are pretty standardised and well defined for cBioPortal (see file-formats). For the clinical data, cBioPortal offers a flexibility in how users can import the data, with only a few data variables having a ‘forced vocabulary’ (i.e. for some data variables, the codebook variables and definitions are ‘default’ to allow cBioPortal to recognise from which items to create standard visualisations such as Kaplan-Meier plots for Overall Survival, Progression/Disease Free Survival). It is up to the users to standardise and harmonise the clinical data variables; this, for instance, will facilitate the use of the ‘across study comparisons’ functionality of cBioPortal, in which study data from multiple studies can be selected to create one larger ‘combined study’ – where users can easily view, query and analyse all the available data as a whole.

To illustrate where data standardisation and harmonisation is important: if study 1 reports ‘tumour diagnosis’ using variables in line with ICD-10, and study 2 reports ‘tumour diagnosis’ through custom-

defined fields in a country's natural language (Dutch, Spanish, French and so on) instead of the same ICD-10 variables, cBioPortal will list the reported variables 'as is', limiting the study-view and comparison capabilities.

In Can.Heal, researchers are aligning to adopt and/or otherwise create standardised and harmonised codebooks so that data can be reported in a uniform format and comparisons of data of multiple studies can be made easier. With respect to reporting ctDNA results captured longitudinally in particular: NKI has participated in Can.Heal and other projects, such as COIN and EOSC4Cancer, and our team has investigated how ctDNA results could be represented in cBioPortal so that this data type could be viewed and queried along with the clinical, biosample and other molecular types of data acquired in the ctDNA studies. The Dutch national cBioPortal instance already accommodates cohort data of various Dutch multicentre ctDNA studies, such as PLCRC-DOLPHIN, PLCRC-MEDOCC, PLCRC-PROVENC3, CAIRO5, and CAIRO6. These ctDNA studies can be easily found in cBioPortal by searching for "ctDNA" in the search box.

From our modelling efforts and the desire to have such data captured in a standardised and harmonised manner for transnational use, we recommend the following to researchers here in Can.Heal:

To enable modelling of longitudinal ctDNA results – using cBioPortal file formats as a leading example - this requires at least three types of files as described on the file-formats page mentioned above:

- (1) a sample data file (containing sample-level information such as the quantity and quality of the detected ctDNA)
- (2) a timeline data file (containing the date of ctDNA collection), and
- (3) a mutation file (providing details of the detected mutations, including the variant allele count and reference allele count).

The ctDNA collection date can be converted into a timeline data file for cBioPortal, enabling the visualisation of molecular testing timelines at the patient level. Information regarding the sequencing technique used, as well as the quantity and quality of ctDNA, can be uploaded as sample attributes. Detected mutations can be converted into a cBioPortal mutation data file; however, external sources are required to provide additional information about variant classifications (e.g., missense, nonsense, etc.). By uploading the mutation data file along with the timeline data, ctDNA levels can be visualised over time for individual patients (Fig. 12).

The raw data to be uploaded and visualized in this format are being provided in D23, being submitted in the next few days.

Fig. 12: An example of longitudinal ctDNA visualisation in the ‘patient view’ section of cBioPortal. The patient’s ctDNA levels are displayed over time in the allele frequency plot, highlighted by the yellow box in the centre of the screenshot. The plot shows variant allele frequency (VAF) ranging from 0 to 1, representing the frequency of measured mutations in samples collected at different time points. Samples are displayed in chronological order, corresponding to the timeline plot above, on which also information of other events are displayed (e.g. surgery, treatment, withdrawal of multiple biopsies over time). This overview provides some insight into possible relations between increase/decrease of ctDNA levels compared to other events. The samples in the allele frequency plot are categorised by sample class (i.e. sample type), represented by blue, red, and orange data points for tissue, cell pellet, and cell-free plasma samples, respectively. Each dot represents a mutation, and lines connect samples of the same sample class that share a particular mutation. Hovering over the data points provides additional information, such as the detected protein change. More detailed mutation data can be found in the mutation section at the bottom of the screenshot.

Main achievements and lessons learnt

Standardization & Documentation:

- Sharing pilot synopses, laboratory protocols, and MTA templates is necessary for efficiency, but not sufficient. The DPOs in particular, much more than Ethical Committees, adopt a variety of procedures that need harmonization. It is highly unlikely that this harmonization might take place peripherally at the level of single networks/pilots/trials. Rather, it is mandatory that minimal essential consensus elements are agreed at the EU level and that MTA/DTA templates are prepared, on the model of Grant Agreements that presently discipline obligations in the context of EU Consortia. Ideally, this template should allow gathering consensus on a single MTA/DTA format, with minor deviations. Deviations, if any, should be annotated at pilot activation in this single document, to be then circulated and signed by all partners. The Can.HEAL Consortium is aware of the challenge intrinsic in this procedure. We have developed considerable expertise on the common issues generating conflicts and delays (see bullet points above), and will report in due time on specific recommendations to mitigate all of them.

Data Protection Officer (DPO) Engagement:

- Proactively engage DPOs early in the process and emphasize their role in finding flexible, compliant solutions. In the present pilot, it was possibly unclear to the DPOs and supporting personnel that the decision to stipulate bilateral agreements would have an avalanche effect on the entire pilot.
- Increase awareness of DPO capabilities, and encourage "out of the box" thinking. Many requests for amendments were possibly the result of a poor communication among the clinical, biotech teams and the DPOs. Better information would have resulted in better framing of the legal issues, preventing many delays.

Dedicated Project Management:

- Implement dedicated project management to ensure consistent follow-up, timely communication, and proactive issue resolution across all project phases. Linked to the above, it will be mandatory that any multi-center trial (particularly with a complex set of shared data) are continuously monitored by a steering board including DPO's representatives to promptly manage unexpected issues.

Dedicated Laboratory Resources:

- Allocate dedicated laboratory personnel for sample management (inbound and outbound) to minimize delays and ensure proper handling. This may help to reduce the timing of sample preparation and shipment.

Impact

The process of data sharing has been delayed. This prevented completion of the entire 'loop' of data exchange. However, the bottlenecks in the path leading to data sharing have been mostly identified and the Consortium is ready to emanate recommendations and good practices that may result in efficient management of data workflow.

Despite delays, major deviations, and failure in some areas, most (80%) activities were completed. Overall, for the specific Can.HEAL pilots we will not be able to generate and share data within the time allotted, and by the end of the project. However, the technical obstacles to data sharing have been identified, and the above major limitations will not prevent reporting and dissemination in the next few months after the end of the project. Most importantly, the Can.HEAL partners have now identified original strategies to coordinate and expedite the MTA/DTA/DPA/SLA process. To our knowledge, such an extensive troubleshooting had not been attempted earlier. D25 was submitted with a significant delay.

References

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